

BRAND LOYALTY AND CONSUMER MOTIVATION: INSIGHTS FROM THE FAST-MOVING CONSUMER GOODS INDUSTRY IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14777529

Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the effect of Motivation on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Motivation strategies employed by FMCGs firms in reaching out to its customers were used as pre-determined factors in measuring brand loyalty. These strategies formed the independent variables for the study which were rewards, and incentives and bonuses. The dependent variable was brand loyalty. The study adopted a descriptive research design and the population of the study consisted of 270 consumers of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State. A purposive sampling technique was adopted by the researchers. Data for the study were collected using structured copies of questionnaire from two hundred and seventy (270) respondents. The research hypothesis was tested using simple regression model at a 5% level of significance. From the data analysis, findings revealed that the motivation significantly affect brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) in Akwa Ibom State. From the findings, it was concluded that motivation affect consumer's brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on this, it was recommended that FMCGs firms should continue to give out incentives and rewards to their customers to build up their brand loyalty.

Keywords: Motivation, Brand Loyalty, Fast-Moving Consumer's Goods

INTRODUCTION

The country Nigeria is nominated by Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs). Fast-moving consumer goods or consumer packaged goods (CPG) are products that are sold quickly and at reasonably low cost. They are retail goods that are generally replaced or fully used up over a short period of time i.e., days, weeks, or months, and one year. This contrasts with durable goods or major appliances such as kitchen appliances, which are generally replaced over a period of several years. Examples of some of the non-durable goods are: soft drinks, over-the-counter drugs, toiletries, processed foods and abundant other consumables. The FMCG have a short shelf life, either as a result of high consumer demand or because the product deteriorates rapidly. Some Fast-Moving Consumer Goods includes alcohol, toiletries, prepackaged foods, soft drinks and cleaning products. In Nigeria, FMCGs account for more than half of all consumers spending, but they tend to be low-involvement purchases. The market size for FMCGs spans around to the population size of 120 million people, based on the FMCG industry analysis in Nigeria of 2019 (Sampson, Udonde and Udoh, 2023).

In a conscious attempt to make a purchase decision for FMCGs, consumers are loyal to brands who encourage them to purchase their products through incentives, rewards and bonuses. Competition in Fast-Moving Consumer Goods sectors are very high and to make purchases consumers have resorted to patronizing brands who only motivate them to choose their brands. Motivation here is encouraging consumers to use or buy the product, and there are many examples of that, such as free gifts, advertising campaigns, the use of product launches, events, or even offering samples of products or exceptional and attractive offers in exchange for buying or trying the product (Mohr, 2017). Many organizations are interested in this trend of buzz marketing as it offers many incentives to individuals through the deployment of the product orally and the interest in promoting products via social networks (Hashem, 2021). It comes in form of grants and reward. People who carry out promotional campaigns for the organizations have individual motivations to participate in obtaining rewards and incentives and in assisting other customers in identifying the brand and its acquisition and preference over other brands.

Brand loyalty has been central to marketing research because of its close relationship to marketing performance. Although scholars have identified many drivers of brand loyalty, they have only recently begun to explore the role of incentives and rewards among consumers for brand loyalty. For example, consumers may remain loyal to a brand if the brand occasionally give them bonuses or grants for making purchases. Loyalty programs are a marketing tactic aimed at building and maintaining brand loyalty through a planned reward scheme based on customers' purchase history. Loyalty programs have been adopted by a wide array of industry sectors (e.g., retail, travel/hospitality, and financial services), and have become increasingly popular among consumers. An integral element of loyalty programs is the achievement of prespecified rewards by meeting the required number of purchases and, for this reason, loyalty programs are often called motivation.

In this regard, incentives and reward has been considered as the best way of increasing loyalty of organizations and brands. With the intense competition in the markets, many companies are trying to implement the strategies of bonuses, rewards and incentives while reducing cost and increasing its brand loyalty. Based on this, the research was conducted to investigate the effect of motivation (with a special focus on Reward and Incentives and Bonuses) on brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods firms in in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of Motivation on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research was designed to:

1. Examine the effect of Reward on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
2. Determine the effect of Incentives and Bonuses on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated from the objectives of the study;

1. To what extent does Reward affect Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does Incentives and Bonuses Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research objective and the research question, the null hypothesis was formulated for the study.

HO₁: Reward has no significant effect on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

HO₂: Incentives and Bonuses has no significant effect on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE**Concept of Motivation**

Motivation is an attribute that moves one to do or not to do something (Udonde, Akpan and Awah, 2022). It is an internal state that drives people to identify and buy a product that fulfil conscious and unconscious needs or desires. It involves encouraging customers to purchase a brand's product rather than the competitive ones. Motivation is a powerful energy that drives and excites customers which results in their maximum loyalty. Human beings are complex in nature and sometimes their actions are driven by their desires and needs.

Motivation here is encouraging consumers to use or buy the product, and there are many examples of that, such as free gifts, advertising campaigns, the use of product launches, events, or even offering samples of products or exceptional and attractive offers in exchange for buying or trying the product (Mohr, 2017). Therefore, producers have to create an atmosphere where customers choose their products and remain loyal to them. Many organizations are interested in this trend towards buzz marketing as it offers many incentives to individuals through the deployment of the product orally and the interest in promoting products via social networks (Hashem, 2021). It comes in form of grants and reward. People who carry out promotional campaigns for the organizations have individual motivations to participate in obtaining rewards and incentives and in assisting other customers in identifying the brand and its acquisition and preference over other brands. It is important that producers look at their customers as an important key to the success of an organization and gives them what motivates them to maximize their productivity. Offering incentives and rewards can effectively contribute to consumer's loyalty of a brand.

Proxies of Motivation

Rewards: Reward programs are the point-based programs loyalty programs designed to increase customer engagement and purchases. This is a common tool used to motivate the customers and increase customer engagement. Rewards are powerful tools to influence customer behaviour, loyalty and satisfaction. But not all

rewards are created equal. Depending on your customer segments and the actions the company want to encourage, the firm need to design and deliver rewards that are relevant, meaningful and motivating.

Incentives and Bonuses: These are motivation programs offer to customers to make them complete the necessary action or in response to the previous activity. Businesses rely on various incentives strategies according to their consumer's unique needs and target audiences. Common customer incentives programs encompass many forms of monetary discounts, referral bonuses, membership benefits, complimentary upgrades, coupons and goods rewards. Discounts can serve as incentives to attract new consumers, foster customer loyalty and expedite the sale of stagnant inventory. Adopting incentives and bonuses by organisation can help customer loyalty and more customer's engagement

Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty refers to attachment a customer has towards a brand. Horsfall (2020) identifies brand loyalty as the connection that a client has to a brand. Brand loyalty is a deeply held duty to repurchase or re-patronize a preferred product or service reliably. Later on, in this way bringing about reputation of same-brand set purchasing, despite situational impact and influence marketing having the capacity to cause exchanging habit.

Brand loyalty is the penchant to be loyal to a brand and this is illustrated by the consumer's intent to acquire the brand as a matter of resolution. Brand loyalty can be both behavioral and attitudinal. Behavioral loyalty embraces unflinching purchase of a brand whereas, attitudinal loyalty is the extent of highly strung guarantee as for some defined keenness pooled with the brand (Horsfall, 2020).

The Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) Sector in Nigeria

The term Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs) refers to those retail goods that are generally replaced or fully used up over a short period of time i.e., days, weeks, or months, and one year. This contrasts with durable goods or major appliances such as kitchen appliances, which are generally replaced over a period of several years. The FMCG have a short shelf life, either as a result of high consumer demand or because the product deteriorates rapidly. Some Fast-Moving Consumer Goods includes alcohol, toiletries, prepackaged foods, soft drinks and cleaning products.

In Nigeria, FMCGs account for more than half of all consumers spending, but they tend to be low-involvement purchases. The market size for FMCGs spans around to the population size of 120 million people, based on the FMCG industry analysis in Nigeria of 2019 (Sampson, Udonde and Udoh, 2023).

According to Reddy, Reddy and Kumar (2018), Fast-Moving Consumer Goods have a short shelf life either due to high consumer demand or because the product deteriorates (perishes) quickly. Some Fast-Moving Consumer Goods such as meat, fruits, vegetables, dairy products and baked goods are highly perishable. Other goods such as alcohol, toiletries, prepackaged foods, soft drinks, and cleaning products comparatively have long time utility. Though the profit margin per unit made on Fast-Moving Consumer Goods product is relatively small (more so

for retailers than the producers/suppliers), they are usually sold in huge quantities. Thus, the collective profit on such goods can be substantial.

For the course of this study, consumers of the following FMCGs were used for of the study; Dansa Foods Limited, Yale Foods Ltd, Deli Foods, DuFil Prima Foods, Friesland Campina Wamco Nigeria Plc, OK Foods, La Casera Company Plc, PZ Cussons, Nigerian Breweries, UAC Group, Rites Foods Ltd, Flour Mill, Cadbury, PZ Group, Promasidor Nigeria Limited, CWAY Food and Beverages Nigeria Company Limited, Chi Limited, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Unilever Plc and Dangote Group. These FMCGs were chosen because they are well known brands and they have been in operations for more than 15 years.

Conceptual Model

Figure 2.1: The Link between Motivation and Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization, (2024)

Theoretical Framework Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 1962)

This theory was propounded by Everett M. Rogers in 1962. It appeared in communication and gives an explanation on how an idea or product gains impetus and spreads through a population social system over a period of time. Being part of the social system, people adopt new ideas, behavior or product as a result of this diffusion. Adoption entails altering previous performances like acquiring a new behavior, buying or using a new product etc. Diffusion is seen to be possible only if individuals perceive ideas, behaviors, or products as new. In a social system, adopting an innovation does not happen simultaneously, it is rather a process where some individuals adopt the innovation more quickly than others.

The diffusion of innovations theory examines the manner new ideas, practices, and objects spread among a network of people via interpersonal and mass communication. Four main elements are used to describe this. The first is the innovation that entails idea, practice or object seen as new by people or other units of adoption which are relevant. The second element is the channel through which communication takes place. The third element considered is the time period. Diffusion of innovation is said to happen overtime and among the members of a social system (Rogers, 1962). In their study on the adoption rate of new medical procedures of rural doctors, Rogers (1962) discovered how ideas are passed between social groups, and noted that word of mouth communication can fit into the diffusion model when connected to interpersonal communication and in a case where mass communication is involved.

According to Rogers (1962), diffusion of innovations happens when consumers go through a mental process through which an individual passes from first hearing about an innovation to final adoption. Consumers have the privilege to make their own decisions about the information they receive. This will help them decide whether or not they will adopt the innovation given the meanings and consequences of other decisions. Individuals go through stages of decisions such as problem conservation, analyzing the problem, deciding the courses of action available, taking action, and accepting the consequences that come as a result of those decisions, before they can be seen as individuals who have completed an adoption (Rogers, 1962).

Typically, Consumers adoption rates tend to be different. According to Rogers (1962) they are classified as innovators (about 2.5 percent of the population), early adopter (about 13 percent of the population), early majority (about 34 percent of the population), late majority (about 13 percent of the population), and laggards (about 16 percent of the population). Each of them holds numerous, but different features along the adoption curve. This is an indication that diffusion of innovation is not just a technical matter, but a social process. Ideas are also regarded as innovations, hence the consideration of viral marketing as an innovation. Just as new products can be diffused among consumers, viral marketing can also be diffused among consumers, viral marketing can also be diffused through agencies. Here public relations agencies are consumers trying out viral marketing for the first time. Innovation adoption relies on relative advantage and complexity. Relative advantage refers to the manner in which an adopter sees the innovation to be superior to other previous methods of completing a task. Complexity on the other hand refers to the level of difficulty of use and implementation of the innovation in the perspective of the adopter. These two factors play a large role in deciding if an agency would adopt buzz marketing. In a case where a relative advantage and low complexity is perceived by the practitioner, buzz marketing will be likely adopted, and vice versa.

Empirical review

Sarker and Rahman (2017) carried out an empirical study on consumers' purchasing decision toward Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs): The study mainly addressed the performance related issues about what extent is the

impact of various factors responsible in terms of consumers' purchasing decision in FMCG (Fast-Moving Consumer Goods) sector in Comilla. The theoretical framework designed based on the literature review and hence ten hypotheses were developed. The samples were selected by convenience sampling technique. Data were collected from 100 customers under different categories through 18 items questionnaires. The questionnaire developed by exploratory research which were used to measure consumer buying behavior. Data were analyzed by using SPSS 16.0 version. The result of the multiple regression analysis showed that there is a significant relationship between dependent variable (Consumers' purchasing decision) and independent variables (Cost, Product Variety, Salesperson, Product Quality, Advertising, Product Display, Income Level, Demand, Familiar Retailers, and Personality). The findings of the study showed that nine out of ten variables were positively related to consumers' purchasing decision but individual personality of respondents has no significant effect on purchasing decision. Therefore, the results of the study definitely play a vital role and leave an ever-lasting impact to use in decision making by consumers and the entire FMCG Company. Moreover, this study can be used as a reference for the future studies to understand the behavior and opinions of the consumers.

Dhanaraj (2020) studied consumer brand awareness of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) in India. The objective of the study was to understand the buying perception of the rural and urban consumer towards FMCG Products. The methodology of the study is based on the primary, as well as secondary data. The study depends mainly on the primary data collected through a structured interview schedule, The secondary data are collected from journals, magazines, publications, reports, books, dailies, periodicals, articles, research papers, websites, company publications, manuals and booklets. The study area comprises of four divisions of erode district and they are classified by the researcher to justify the sampling procedure adopted in the research. Proportionate random sampling methods have been used to collect various perceptions of consumers of FMCG in rural and urban areas in erode district. Erode District consists of 14 blocks in which 10 villages were selected through lottery method from each block. The sample size of 600 respondents, representing 10 from 60 villages has been proportionately chosen from sampling. The primary data collected from the consumers will be analyzed by using SPSS V-15 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) to obtain the results concerning the objectives of the study. Factor analysis, Cluster analysis, t-test, One Way Analysis of Variance, Multiple Regression and Correspondence and Association Analysis are applied for analyzing the responses of FMCG consumers of Erode District. In conclusion, the study established the relationship between the various factors affecting consumers and their awareness preferences in buying FMCG brands using rural buyers as sample. This research study also identifies the factors influencing consumer preferences in making decision to buy FMCG brands. Studying differences among consumers of diverse socio-economic categories on factors influencing their awareness and preferences for FMCG brands is a significant contribution to examine the differences among users with various levels of exposure and preferences.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was conducted using the descriptive research design. The descriptive research design enables the researcher to collect data from all aspect of the variables through a structured questionnaire.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of all consumers of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Sampling and Sample Size Determination

Given the largeness of the infinite population, it would be impossible to carry out a study of the whole population. The sample size was determined using the Top-man Formula for sample sizes were the population is finite but not known. $n = \frac{Z^2 (pq)}{e^2}$

Where n=sample size

Z=value of Z-score associated with the selected degree of confidence (1.96 for 95% Confidence level)
e=estimated standard error (5%) p=probability of success (0.5) q=probability of failure (1-p)

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5) (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416) (0.5) (0.5)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 384.16$$

Since the sample size cannot be in fraction or decimal, the sample size will be approximated to the nearest whole numbers. Thus, $n = 384.16 = 384$ (approximation). Therefore, the sample size of 384 respondents was used, where 384 copies of questionnaire were administered to the consumers of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods firms in Akwa Ibom State.

Sampling Procedures/ Research Instrumentation

Using convenient sampling, 384 respondents were chosen from different locations in Akwa Ibom State. Out of the 384 respondents, 270 copies of questionnaire were successfully retrieved and used for the study.

In conducting this study, a fully structured questionnaire was used as an instrument in order to gather information from the respondents. It consisted of the closed-ended multiple choice questions and Likert-scale questions which enable respondents to express their level of agreement and select the answer that suits them best. The questionnaire was structured using the five-point Likert scale rated as follows:

5 = Very High Extent

4 = High Extent

3 = Moderate Extent

2 = Low Extent

1 = Very Low Extent

Validity of the Instrument

The questionnaire had to undergo face and content validity before being administered on the respondents. The content validity was estimated as the questionnaire items were scrutinized by four senior lecturers in the department of marketing.

Reliability of the Instrument

Using the internal consistency reliability, the research instrument was assessed to ascertain the effect between multiple items in the test that are intended to measure the same construct. The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was adopted with an alpha coefficient benchmark of 0.76 to calculate in terms of average, the inter-correlations among the items measuring the concept.

Empirical Specification of Model

The model for the study and all the variables are stated below:

The dependent variable was: Brand Loyalty (BL) while the independent variables were: Reward (R) and Incentives and Bonuses (IB). Below is the model:

$$BL = \beta_0 + \beta_1 R + \beta_2 IB + e_t \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (3.1)},$$

Where: β_0 = Intercept of BL; β_1 and β_2 = Coefficient of each of the independent variables; e_t = Random error terms.

Method of Data Analysis

The questionnaire was edited for consistency and completeness, data were analyzed and explained to suit the objectives. The simple linear regression model was used to analyze the data collected and test the hypotheses stated as well and with the help of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS-version 25). The level of significance was 5%.

Decision Criteria

The decision making on the result will depend on the p-value outcome. When the P-value is higher than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis will be rejected. But when the P-value is less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis will be accepted.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis One

HO₁: Reward has no significant effect on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model Summary Showing the Effect of Reward on Brand Loyalty of FMCGs Firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Reward	.	Enter

	Dimensions ^b		
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- a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty Dimensions
b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary Showing the Effect of Reward on Brand Loyalty of FMCGs Firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.838 ^a	.702	.701		.36611

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Reward Dimensions

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA^a) Showing the Effect of Reward on Brand Loyalty of FMCGs Firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria .

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	84.558	1	84.558	630.875	.000 ^b
Residual	35.921	268	.134		
Total	120.479	269			

- a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty Dimensions
b. Predictors: (Constant), Reward Dimensions

Coefficients^a Showing the Effect of Reward on Brand Loyalty of FMCGs Firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.247	.110		2.243	.026
Reward Dimensions	.884	.035	.838	25.117	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty Dimensions

Source: Researcher's Computation, (2024)

The Table 4.1 with R value of 0.838 indicated that there is a significant influence between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.702 implies that about 70.2% of the variation in Brand Loyalty was explained by Reward dimensions. The Calculated value of 630.875 and P-value of 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. That is, the independent variable was able to explain the dependent variable very well. The constant value of 0.247 indicates that keeping independent variable (Reward dimensions) constant, Brand Loyalty

will remain at 0.247. The coefficient of Reward dimensions was 0.884 which means that a unit change in motivation dimensions will lead to 0.884-unit change in Brand Loyalty. The P-value of 0.026 means that the effect of Reward dimensions on Brand Loyalty was statistically significant.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Incentives and Bonuses has no significant effect on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model Summary Showing the Effect of Incentives and Bonuses on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Incentives and Bonuses Dimensions ^b	.	Enter

- a. Dependent Variable Brand Loyalty Dimensions
b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary Showing the Effect of Incentives and Bonuses on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria .

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.853 ^a	.728	.727		.34972

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Incentives and Bonuses Dimensions

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA^a) showing the Effect of Incentives and Bonuses on Brand Loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.702	1	87.702	717.090	.000 ^b
	Residual	32.777	268	.122		
	Total	120.479	269			

- a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty Dimensions
b. Predictors: (Constant), Incentives and Bonuses Dimensions

Coefficients^a showing the Effect of Incentives and Bonuses on Brand Loyalty of Fast-moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	.101	.109		.923	.000
Incentives and Bonuses Dimensions	.951	.035	.853	26.779	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty Dimensions

Source: Researcher's Computation, (2024)

The Table 4.2 with R value of 0.853 indicated that there is a significant influence between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.728 implies that about 72.8% of the variation in Brand Loyalty was explained by Incentives and Bonuses dimensions. The F-calculated value of 717.090 and P-value of 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. That is, the independent variable was able to explain the dependent variable very well. The constant value of 0.101 indicates that keeping independent variable (Incentives and Bonuses dimensions) constant, Brand Loyalty will remain at 0.101. The coefficient of Incentives and Bonuses dimensions was 0.951 which means that a unit change in Incentives and Bonuses dimensions will lead to 0.951-unit change in Brand Loyalty. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of Incentives and Bonuses dimensions on Brand Loyalty was statistically significant.

Discussion of the Findings

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of motivation on Brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. To achieve the study objectives, a simple linear regression model was used to test each independent variables against the dependent variable. The findings revealed that Motivation significantly affects Brand Loyalty of FMCGs in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This implies that awarding customers with gifts for buying a product can help increase their loyalty for the brand.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The main aim of this study was to examine the effect of motivation on Brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The data collected were analyzed with the help of a simple linear regression model. From the analysis of data, the independent variable (Motivation) had a positive and significant effect on the dependent variables (Brand Loyalty). This implies that awarding customers with gifts for buying a product can help increase their Loyalty for the brand.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that motivation affect consumer's brand loyalty of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings, it was recommended that FMCGs firms should continue to give out incentives and rewards to their customers to build up their brand loyalty.

REFERENCES

- Dhanaraj, V.T. (2020). A study on consumer brand awareness of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG). *Journal of Information and Computational Science*, 10 (10); 171-181
- Hashem, T.N (2021). The role of buzz marketing in increasing attention towards green products, moderating role of shockvertising. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(2); 1785-1798.
- Horsfall, H. (2020). Brand equity and brand performance of retail pharmaceutical firms in Rivers State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Innovation*, 3(1); 100-112.
- Mohr, I. (2017). Managing buzz marketing in the digital age. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 11(2); 10 – 16.
- Reddy, T. N., Reddy, M. V. B. & Kumar, P. L. M. (2018). A study on Fast-Moving consumer goods sector- A comparative study on dairy and soft drink products. *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development (IJMPERD)*, 8 (2); 157-160.
- Sampson, E.A., Udonde, U.E. & Udoh, I.E. (2023). The interplay of pricing strategies and sales volume of Fast-Moving consumer goods in Calabar metropolis. *International Journal of Academic Accounting, Finance & Management Research (IJAAFMR)*, 7(7); 32-38.
- Udonde, U. E., Akpan, A.O & Awah, A. E (2022). Internal marketing and employee performance in insurance industry in Nigeria. *British International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 5(01); 1-22.